

Where was the Battle of Munda fought?

The great mystery of the past 2,071 years. I'm going to put forward my own proposal, based on what others have thought before me, on a literal reading of the classical sources, and on a review of LiDAR maps using modern AI algorithms.

What I'm about to formulate is a hypothesis, but I have one advantage: in the worst case, I'll achieve the same result as the greatest expert who ever attempted the same exercise—none.

Why does Munda matter?

It is Caesar's last battle. At Munda he defeated what was left of the Pompeian armies and finished off the last opposition the *optimates* could throw at him. He emerged as the sole power in Rome, and from that moment until his assassination he ruled without opposition. On top of that, he faced **Titus Labienus**, his former second-in-command in the Gallic War and the general many considered the true military genius of those campaigns. As if that weren't enough, Labienus and Pompey the Younger forced Caesar to fight the hardest battle of his life. According to Plutarch, Caesar said that in every other battle he had fought for victory; at Munda, he had to fight for his life. It was so hard that he had to deal with part of his own line breaking, take up arms himself, and by his example bring the troops back into the fight. The outcome was uncertain until the very end and he could very easily have lost. Only the discipline and skill of the X Legion saved Caesar from disaster.

Why is it a mystery?

Because we are not sure where the *city* of Munda was—at whose feet the battle was fought—nor even where the *plain of Munda* mentioned by the classical sources actually lay. Traditionally, **Montilla** (Córdoba, Spain) has been proposed, based on the toponym and its relative proximity to Córdoba, the city of reference in the narrative. But Montilla doesn't fit many parts of the description given by the author of *De Bello Hispaniensi*, the only eyewitness account we have. In the late 20th and early 21st centuries other locations have been proposed, all of them south of Córdoba. Let me invite you to reason

this through with me, and let's see if (1) we land on one of the existing proposals, and (2) whether LiDAR can give us additional data to back up the hypothesis.

Method: literal reading of De Bello Hispaniensi

We're going to rely on *De Bello Hispaniensi* throughout. It's the only truly contemporary source we have, and the one that best describes the manoeuvres before the battle and the battle itself. Unfortunately Caesar himself didn't write it (as he did with *De Bello Gallico*)—it was written by some officer or servant in Caesar's army. The narrative is quite poor and the description of places and events leaves a lot to be desired. Still, it's the only reliable thing we have. Let's start.

Where to look for Munda?

We have two key data points the author gives us. The first is that both Caesar and Pompey had been playing cat-and-mouse without engaging in battle (the translation here is by my AI, and I asked it to be as literal as possible even at the cost of clarity):

Pompey, realising that Ucubi was about to be handed over to us by its inhabitants, gave it to the flames so that it could be of no use to Caesar. From there he marched to the *oppidum* of Ventippo; and at the start of his siege, after the surrender [of the *oppidum* to Caesar], he set out for Carruca and pitched his camp opposite Pompey's. Pompey burned that *oppidum* [Carruca], which had not opened its gates to him; and a centurion of that town who had defected to Pompey, taking him with hands tied, he himself cut off his hands. From that place, Caesar moves to the *campus mundensis* and pitches his camp near the *oppidum* itself [of Munda].

As you can see, the narrative is hard to follow. The first sentence refers to Pompey, the rest to Caesar. **Ucubi** is the modern town of **Espejo** and **Ventippo** is the modern **Casariche**. **Carruca** we don't know. This tells us that they were coming from the east, moving westward, playing cat-and-mouse. Moving away from Córdoba towards Seville (Roman Hispalis).

On the next day, when Caesar wanted to march with his troops, the scouts announced that Pompey had been in battle formation since the third watch. On hearing this news, he hoisted the [combat] flag. Pompey had brought out his troops because he had sent letters to the city of Urso saying that our men [the Caesarians] were facing him but didn't dare to come down to the plain. And by holding back his soldiers in this way, he gained much in authority.

We have here important clues. The townspeople of **Urso** (modern **Osuna**) were afraid, and Pompey sends them a letter to reassure them. This confirms the westward direction. Why were the people of Osuna so frightened that they had to be reassured? There can only be one reason: **Caesar and his army were very close**. Major clue. From the previous paragraph we already know Caesar and Pompey had their camps facing each other, so we're narrowing down the area of the battle. But there's more:

Thus, taking advantage of the moment, [Pompey] advanced from the plain to a high hill, where he stationed his troops. A plain of about five miles lay between the two camps, so that Pompey's auxiliary troops were defended by two things: by the *oppidum* and by the

nature of the high ground. From here, extending out, the adjacent plain was levelled. And preceding their descent there was a stream which made the approach extremely disadvantageous: for it ran through marshy and boggy ground on the right. So Caesar, seeing the line drawn up, had no doubt that the enemy would come out to fight in the middle of the plain, on level ground. This was visible to all.

More clues. Pompey climbs a hill without losing sight of Caesar. The author says that hill was an *oppidum*. This implies a previously fortified town. If it were untouched ground and Pompey simply pitched his camp there, the author would say *castra*. But no—it's an *oppidum*: he's making use of an already existing fortified town. Several additional details we'll need: *the oppidum* was defended by the nature of the place and by the city's own defences. **Keep in mind the key detail that on Caesar's line of advance there was a stream on the right that troubled him a great deal and that led to marshy and boggy ground.**

I'll skip the battle for now. Caesar wins. Titus Labienus dies, Pompey dies, and another Roman general—**Varus**—also dies. The survivors take refuge in the *oppidum* of Munda, but eventually surrender. Some flee to Córdoba, others to Osuna. Caesar takes Córdoba and Sevilla easily now that there's no Pompeian army in the field, but one place is still holding out: **Osuna**.

The *oppidum* of Urso is splendidly protected by the nature of the place, and even the very nature of the place was an obstacle to the enemy's siege: for, besides the fact that the *oppidum* was high, set on raised ground, the *agger* [defensive wall/rampart] was built of stone. And the timber with which siege towers are normally built could not be found within six miles. Pompey, moreover, in order to make the position of the *oppidum*—already protected by nature—even safer, had felled all the timber around it and stockpiled it inside the *oppidum*. Thus our men were forced to bring timber from Munda, which they had recently captured, all the way there [Urso].

Here, without meaning to, the author gives us a key piece of information. **In Osuna there was no timber for siege engines. There was no timber within six miles.** So the Caesarians had to bring it from Munda—meaning they used the timber that had formed the defences of Munda's *oppidum*. **We need to look for Munda about seven Roman miles from Osuna.**

Recap

We have all the data we need. Let's pull it together:

- *Munda must be near Osuna, around 7 Roman miles away.*
- *It must sit on a hill where there was a previous oppidum.*
- *Caesar's camp must have been about 5 Roman miles from Munda.*
- *On the route from Caesar's camp to Munda we must find a stream on the right that troubled Caesar greatly.*
- *There must be marshy and boggy ground.*

· *Both Pompey's position and Caesar's must be large enough to host their massive armies. More than 40 hectares—possibly twice that—but we shouldn't forget that the two armies had been facing each other for some time and weren't in a position to choose perfect ground or build a textbook camp. As in the Cantabrian Wars, we'll need to see how they adapted to the terrain rather than how they adapted the terrain to themselves.*

Step one: the marshy ground

I'll start with the easy bit: the marshy and boggy ground. North of Osuna there's an area visible on Google Maps as [Complejo Endorreico Lantejuela](#)—clearly a low-lying basin where water pools, with permanent natural lagoons.

So that's where we'll look. We're not far off, because there are already authors who have proposed Munda must have been near Lantejuela. For example the **Sociedad Arqueológica Sevillana** in 1870 proposed that Munda had to be at the [Cerro de la Camorra](#), just north of the endorheic basin. I ran the LiDAR over that hill and found nothing—just bare hillside.

Looking at SLR and VAT LiDAR views of the hill, what we see is a modest natural elevation with some relief—but no fortified perimeter, no defensive step, no enveloping crest-and-ditch system, no defined summit platform. The textures that do appear are agricultural (historical parcels, old paths) along with a couple of modern water cisterns. At 180 m of altitude and just +40 m of relief over the surroundings, the Cerro de la Camorra falls well short of the profile we'd expect for a Turdetan *oppidum* capable of hosting thirteen legions.

This place doesn't seem to be the Oppidum of Munda because it is not even a good defensive position. The hill is too low.

We need to keep looking. At this point we need the [EasyLidar with AI](#) software for Mac. We have to start feeding it the Spanish [Instituto Geográfico Nacional](#) tiles for the area. As I said, north of the endorheic basin there's nothing eye-catching—just olive-grove hills. The surprise comes on a hill **7.9 Roman miles north of Osuna**: the Spanish official maps call it [Cerro de la Quinta](#).

At first glance there's nothing there. On Google Maps it doesn't even have a name. Olive groves on top of olive groves.

The interesting stuff appears once we apply the LiDAR views that bring out micro-relief and details that aerial photography can't capture. In the SLRM view a clear line appears around the hill, defining its mid-slope:

If we overlay the cadastre in EasyLidar, we see this delineation **doesn't follow any single property line, but it does determine sides of several adjacent parcels**. That means the feature was almost certainly there *before* the parcels were laid out, but wasn't built to delimit any of them:

In the VAT composite view the traces are very clear: there's a sharp break where the hillside descent suddenly steepens.

Let's look at a longitudinal cross-section produced by the software. If we walked east-to-west across the slope, what would we find?

The ascent has a steady slope of about 5%, but at the points marked by the LiDAR figure it jumps to 40%. There's a clear step that has obviously been worn down by time and was probably closer to vertical centuries ago. Now the same north-to-south:

Same pattern—and on the south side the step is double. There’s no doubt in my mind that this isn’t natural, because **it doesn’t follow the geometric forms of the terrain**. We’ve found what was probably an ancient *oppidum* occupied by native peoples since antiquity. Let’s see if it fits what we’re looking for:

- Located *7.9 Roman miles (11.7 km)* from the centre of modern Osuna.
- The town inside the figure measured about *40 hectares*.

· The 40 ha is the bounded enclosure, but the hill itself is much larger—around 200 hectares of high ground.

· It sits *right next to a natural endorheic lagoon*. When the water layer is overlaid in EasyLidar this is very clear. It's also clear that this body of water is fed by a stream that runs along the north of the hill (where the arrows point).

Assuming Pompey was to the west and Caesar was pursuing him from the east, we have a strong candidate for the *oppidum* of Munda that satisfies everything the chronicler says—including the stream on the right that troubled Caesar so much in the battle and which led to the marshy ground. We also have the place where the timber for the siege of Osuna came from: at 7.9 Roman miles, fitting the chronicler's range. Although I haven't marked them with arrows, to the right of the figure you can clearly see traces of rampart-ditch-rampart structures (white-dark-white lines) that may be man-made or natural—to me they look man-made—and that match the description of the defences Caesar's army had to push through on its advance.

Step two: testing the hypothesis with Caesar's camp

We've found a good candidate, but let's test it. If that was the *oppidum* of Munda, we should find Caesar's camp to the east (right in the image). The chronicler told us 5 Roman miles separated them. Let's see what's at 5 Roman miles (7.4 km) from this hill...

...exactly **7 km east** of the hill there's another set of interconnected hills, headed by one called **Cerro de las Cabezas**.

From the wide LiDAR view above you'll already have seen the [Cerro de las Cabezas](#) glowing—let's zoom in:

It glows like that because **the scarps are imposing**. That's not natural either. **That hill was worked in antiquity to give it those imposing scarps**. If we accept this hypothesis, Caesar also chose an existing *oppidum* to station his troops. In fact, despite all the intensive agricultural activity in the area, in some places you can still see attempts at a ditch-rampart defensive system (take a look to the arrows):

It measures **9.5 ha**, but it's connected to the cluster of hills behind in an elevated platform above the plain that brings the available area to **170 ha**. There's room for a huge army there. The author, when speaking of Caesar's camp, says *castra* and not *oppidum*—meaning *most of Caesar's army may have been on the hills behind Cerro de las Cabezas*. An army the size of Caesar's would need around 80 ha to deploy.

It would be reasonable to expect mutual visibility between the two camps. Fortunately the software has a tool for line-of-sight checks, and **yes—there is full visibility** in both directions.

We have another good candidate for Caesar's camp. Let's review:

· It's about 5 Roman miles from the Cerro de la Quinta where we propose the Munda oppidum.

· It's 12 km from Osuna, which would explain very well the nervousness of Osuna's inhabitants—they were Pompey's allies.

And what about the route between them? Let's see if it matches what the chronicler says.

We have all the elements. According to this hypothesis, Caesar's army was **bounded by two streams**, although it's true that the northern stream (the Caesarian right) is much wider than the southern one.

Pompey waited high up the slope, but probably in front of the defensive step we've been examining. As they climbed, Caesar's men, on top of the gradient, encountered the rampart–ditch–rampart features we saw on LiDAR. The Pompeians would have used that ground to throw everything they had at the Caesarians.

A note on Varus's pin

I still need to deal with *Varus's pin* (pasador de Varo). **As it turns out, those who proposed the Cerro de la Camorra as Munda (Durán Recio and others) have a material find on their side: a clasp/pin was discovered there with the initials A. VARO—Varus, one of Pompey's lieutenants. This doesn't worry me for my hypothesis.** Varus, in the rout, tried to escape. **He was caught and beheaded by Caesar's soldiers, who took his head to their chief.** It was during that flight and killing that he lost the pin. That his clasp ended up east of Munda is consistent with him fleeing eastward after the battle was lost.

The end of Munda

The end of Munda was dramatic. After the Pompeian army was defeated and its leaders killed:

With this battle concluded, the rest took refuge in the *oppidum* of Munda, where we were forced to circumvallate them. With the enemies' weapons, corpses were placed instead of turf, and shields and javelins instead of palisade; on top, the heads of the

dead, arranged on the points of swords, were turned towards the *oppidum*—so that the besieged might see the appearance of fear in their enemies and the signs of [our men's] courage, and so that [the *oppidum*] might be encircled with such a palisade.

The *oppidum* of Munda didn't hold out long. Some **14,000 people had taken refuge inside Munda. Fabius Maximus**, one of Caesar's lieutenants, stayed behind to take the city. After a few days of siege, the people inside Munda fought among themselves and a slaughter took place inside the city. A few of them tried to break the cordon and flee. The Caesarians took advantage of the chaos to seize the town and **capture the 14,000 people still inside Munda**. We don't know what happened to them, but it's unlikely to have been pleasant. By that point in the civil war Caesar was no longer in the mood to forgive his enemies.

If you liked the hypothesis (or didn't), please leave something in the comments—it helps Google's algorithm push the page up the search results.